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CLINICAL PHARMACIST IS KEY ROLE OF THE PATIENT-CENTERED CARE IN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITALS IN INDIAN SENERIO

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ABSTRACT

Pharmacist traditionally involving compounding, production and dispensing of drugs from ancient times. As the diseases and sedentary life style leads to complications to use of more medications to manage the disease and life style problems, this is the time to identify the unsafe and irrationalize medicine medical therapy has emerged. This has also contributed to clinical pharmacists being more involved in patient-centered pharmacotherapy. A large literature documents the multiple roles clinical pharmacists can play in a variety of health care settings. The main aim of the study is role of clinical pharmacist in modifying disease outcome by patient centered care in the medical wards. Clinical pharmacist role between physician and patient to provide drug information, economic benefits, patient compliance, drug related problems (DRP), to determine the effect of patient counseling on quality of life of patient. **METHODOLOGY-** The prospective observational study to conducts for a period of two and half years about 30 months in patient departments in a tertiary care hospital in South India. promoting better medication use, ensuring that patients receive appropriate pharmacotherapy, thus minimizing the risk of unfavorable outcomes of pharmacotherapy adherence scale. **RESULTS & DISCUSSION-** A total of 1263 patients out of 6548 inpatients of general medicine department were followed out of which having one or more drug related problems. Female (56.7%) [Table-22] predominance was noted over males (43.3%). Drug related problems were more commonly seen in patients aged between 41-60 years, (47.92 %). A total of 240 drug related problems were identified. Most of the DRP observed in the study resulted from the inappropriate drug dosing problems (25.42%) followed by drug selection (24.16%) [Table-23]. Majority of the clinical pharmacist recommendations were on drug discontinuation (29.58%) and drug doses change (22.6%). **CONCLUSION-** The study concludes that involving clinical pharmacist services in patients care can significantly helps to identify, resolve and prevent the DRPs in the hospital thereby enhancing the patient's outcomes. Furthermore, the suggestions provided by the clinical pharmacist during the intervention were well accepted by the physician thus the collaborative approach of physician and clinical pharmacist can provide better patients centre care outcomes. The study stresses the importance of clinical pharmacist in health care sector and impeccable role in patients care.

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INTRODUCTION

The specialty of clinical pharmacy has evolved from the United States (US), and since the international launch of the pharmaceutical care philosophy by ^[01], underlining the pharmacists' responsibility to guide drug therapy to improve the quality of the patients' life, the role of the pharmacist in pharmaceutical care has been expanding worldwide ^[02]. The availability of rational use of medicines are critical for a successful therapeutic outcome. Though rapid developments in science and technology have led to easy understanding of etiology and pathophysiological basis of various diseases and development of new molecules, many times clinicians fail to achieve the desired therapeutic goals. One of the major reasons for this can be the patient noncompliance or partial compliance towards the prescribed treatment (World Health Organization, 2003).

Patient compliance is defined as the adherence of a patient towards the prescriber's instructions. It implies an understanding of how the medicine is to be used, as well as a positive behavior in which the patient is motivated sufficiently to use the prescribed treatment in the manner intended because of a perceived self-benefit and a positive outcome (e.g. enhanced quality of life and well being). Non-compliance can lead to various consequences including underuse, overuse, misuse, abuse etc ^[03]. The most common factors associated with noncompliance are the nature of the disease, multiple drug therapy, frequency of drug administration, duration of drug therapy, adverse events, cost of medications, administration technique, taste of medication etc. In the present days, the term "concordance" is used more often in place of compliance ^[04].

A large literature documents the multiple roles clinical pharmacists can play in a variety of health care settings^[05]. Much of this literature focuses on measures of impact not directly relevant to this Report-eg, economic benefits, ^[06] patient compliance, and drug monitoring. More recently, systems-based analyses of medication errors and adverse drug events (ADEs) have drawn attention to the impact clinical pharmacists can exert on the quality and safety of medication use ^[07]. In this chapter, we review the evidence supporting the premise that direct participation of pharmacists' in clinical care reduces medication errors and ADEs in hospitalized and ambulatory patients ^[08] ^[09]. Ineffective communication is reported as a significant contributing factor in medical errors and inadvertent patient harm. In addition to causing physical and emotional harm to patients and their families, adverse events are also financially costly ^[10]^[11]. "Ineffective communication is the most frequently cited category of root causes of sentinel events. Effective communication, which is timely, accurate, complete, unambiguous, and understood by the recipient, reduces errors and results in improved patient safety" ^[12]^[13].

The position of the pharmacist within the health care system has continually been subject to change. With respect to drug dispensing several tasks can be distinguish.^[14]

DOSE:

Evaluating if the dose prescribed is recommended in accordance with the literature, considering weight or body surface of the patient, and the necessity for adjustment for altered renal and/or hepatic function;

MEDICATION INTERVAL:

Evaluating if the intervals of administration of prescribed medications were described in the literature, and the possible suitability of the same for abnormal kidney and liver function, also considering the possibility of reducing costs and time spent by nursing administration;

ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION:

Evaluating the route of administration, based on pharmacokinetic characteristics and patient clinical condition;

PRESENTATION AND/OR DOSAGE FORM:

Evaluating if the hospital standardization is adequate according to the patient (children, elderly, patients with swallowing problems or feeding tube);

INAPPROPRIATE/UNNECESSARY MEDICATION:

Evaluating if there is any medication without indication for the clinical condition, therapeutic duplicity, counter indicated or unnecessary medication for the clinical condition of the patient, and patient with known allergic reaction to medication;

NECESSITY OF ADDITIONAL MEDICATION:

Evaluating if there is any untreated medical condition, continued treatment, prophylactic or preventive medication

MORE APPROPRIATE AND/OR ALTERNATIVE THERAPY AVAILABLE:

Evaluating if there is a medication, more effective, cost-effective or safer and available in the hospital standard medication list

DRUG INTERACTIONS:

Evaluating if there is any drug-to drug interaction with clinical relevance according to the classifications found in the databases; inconsistencies in prescription orders: discrepant information about dosing or administration instructions contained in the same medication order

DILUTION AND/OR INFUSION RATE: evaluating the concentration and infusion rate of the medication

PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL INCOMPATIBILITIES AND/OR PREPARATION STABILITY:

Evaluating possible incompatibilities between drugs and drug/diluent and verification of the stability of the medications prescribed in accordance with the standard dilution of each clinic.

Drug related problems may leads to reduced quality of life[15,16] increase hospital stay, overall increase health cost and even increase risk of morbidity and mortality. However, studies shows that majority of Drug-related problems (50-80%) are often preventable, and pharmaceutical services can reduce the number of ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS, the length of hospital stays, and the cost of care [17].

Dunn, S.P. et al. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2015; 66(19):2129-39.

METHODOLOGY

The prospective observational study was conducted for a period of two and half years, about 30 months in inpatient departments in a tertiary care hospital in South India. This study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethical Committee (IHEC), Guntur Medical college, Guntur. All patients of either sex admitted in the different departments of in-patients, during the study period are evaluated, the drugs dispensed according to physician prescription to all in-patients departments.

The clinical pharmacist play a key role in promoting better medication use, ensuring that patients receive appropriate pharmacotherapy, thus minimizing the risk of unfavorable outcomes of pharmacotherapy and consequently reducing costs. Among these activities, the review of medication orders is extremely important, and it enables identifying, solving and preventing the emergence of drug therapy problems (DTP) and negative outcomes associated with medication

Study Design: An Observational Prospective Study

Study Period: January 2014 to June 2016 (30 Months)

Study Site: Government General Hospital (GGH), a 1800 bedded tertiary care teaching hospital, Guntur.

Study Materials: Patient data collection form, Informed consent form, patient education leaflets, patient counseling forms, drug related problems

Inclusion Criteria

- All the patients who are hospitalized and with drug related problems in the in-patient department(s)
- Patients only on allopathic treatment, irrespective of age and gender.
- Healthcare members i.e. medical Interns, Nurses, were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who are on alternative system(s) of medicines.
- Out-patient department patients were excluded.
- Patients unable to explain about the adverse drug reactions

STUDY PROCEDURE

Patients admitted in respective departments were assessed for adverse reactions drug and patient specific information was collected. An informed consent was taken from the patients for participating in the study. The relevant issues related to drug related problems was notified and discussed with the physician. Drug involved in DRPs, types of DRPs, potential issues and the clinical significance level of DRPs, recommendation provided and the acceptance level of physician for the particular intervention. Patient education by using tool-kits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 01: The Demographic Details And Characteristic Of The Patients.

S.No	Details		Number (%) N=1263
1.	Gender	Male	547(43.3%)
		Female	716 (56.7%)
2.	Age (years)	0-20	121 (9.58%)
		21-40	179 (14.17%)
		41-60	605 (47.92%)
		Above 60	358 (28.33%)
3.	Co- morbidity	1	423(35.83%)
		2	721 (57.08%)
		3to 4	78 (6.25%)
		>4	11(0.84%)
4.	Number of drugs received on admission per patient	1-5	432 (34.17%)
		6-10	589 (46.67%)
		>10	242 (19.16%)

A total of 1263 drug related problems were identified from 6548 patients intervened during the study period, in which highly affected were Female patients 716(56.7%) and age group are 41-60 were 605(47.92%) ,with 2 co- morbidities are 721(57.08%) and 6-10medicaton received on admission per patients were 589(46.67%) respectively.

Table 02: Types Of Drug Related Problems Identified.

S.No	Types of DRP'S	No. of DRP'S	Total Number	Percentage(%)N=1263	
1.	Improper Drug selection	a)Drug/therapeutic Duplication	164	306	24.16%
		b)No Drug prescribed but clear indication	21		
		c)Drug prescribed but no clear indication	121		
2.	Compliance problems	Non-adherence	53	53	4.16%
3.	Inappropriate Dosing	a)Prescribed dose high	210	321	25.42%
		b)Incorrect or unclear dosing instructions	111		
4.	Under treated	Condition not adequately treated	68	68	5.42%
5.	Monitoring need	a)Laboratory monitoring	47	68	5.42%
		b)Non-Laboratory monitoring	21		
6.	Interaction	a)Drug-Drug interaction	179	268	21.25%
		b)Drug Disease interaction	89		
7.	Improper Drug use	Drugs not taken/ administered	21	21	1.67%
8.	Toxicity and Side effects	a)Toxicity apparent	16	158	12.5%
		b)Side effects present\	142		

A total of 1263 drug related problems were identified from 6548 patients intervened during the study period, in which, 1 DRP was found in 142 (11.25%) patients, 2 DRPs in 816 (64.58%) patients and 3 DRPs in 305 (24.17%) patients respectively. the types and number of drug related problem identified were characterized as shown in table 02.

Table 03: Clinical Pharmacist Recommendation.

S.No	Types of Recommendation	Number (n=1263)	Percentage (%)
1.	Drug Doses change (dose decrease)	284	22.6%
2.	Drug change	121	9.58%
3.	Drug discontinuation	374	29.58%
4.	Drug addition	63	5%
5.	Dose schedule/frequency change	89	7.08%
6.	Duration change	53	4.17%
7.	Appropriate administration	16	1.25%
8.	Drug monitoring need	121	9.58%
9.	Others	89	7.08%
10	NO RECOMMENDATION	53	4.17%

A total of 1263 recommendations were made to the physician by the clinical pharmacist for 1263 Drug therapy problems. The type of recommendation provided by the attending clinical pharmacist is shown in Table 03.

Table 04: Significance Level of Drug Related Problems.

S.No	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL	NUMBER (%) N= 1263
1.	MINOR	495 (39.17%)
2.	MODERATE	605 (47.92%)
3.	MAJOR	163 (12.91%)

The significance level of intervention was analyzed based on 3 criteria minor, moderate and major. Out of 1263 drug related problems, 495 (39.17%) were minor, 605(47.92 %) were moderate and 163 (12.91 %) were major. The level of significance of drug therapy intervention made is shown in Table 04.

Table 05: Result of Interventions.

S.No	RESULTS	NUMBER (N=1263)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Suggestions accepted and therapy changed	889	70.42%
2.	Suggestions accepted but therapy not changed	242	19.17%
3.	Neither suggestions accepted nor therapy changed	132	10.41%

Out of 1263 recommendations concerning drug related problems 889 (70.42%) of the case suggestion were accepted and therapy was changed, while in 242(19.17%) of cases suggestion were accepted but therapy was not changed where as 132 (10.41%) neither suggestion were accepted nor therapy was changed. The result of clinical pharmacist recommendations is shown in the Table 05.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A total of 1263 patients out of 6548 inpatients of general medicine department were followed out of which having one or more drug related problems. Female (56.7%) [Table-01] predominance was noted over males (43.3%). Drug related problems were more commonly seen in patients aged between 41-60 years, (47.92 %). A total of 240 drug related problems were identified. Most of the DRP observed in the study resulted from the inappropriate drug dosing problems (25.42%) followed by drug selection (24.16%)[Table-02]. Majority of the clinical pharmacist recommendations were on drug discontinuation (29.58%) and drug doses change (22.6%). Moderate significance of DRPs were noted high (47.92 %) [TABLE-04], whereas (39.17 %) were minor and (12.91 %) were major. The acceptance rate of intervening clinical pharmacist recommendation and change in drug therapy was found to be high (70.42%) [Table- 03,05].

As developing country like India, need to be initiate importance of Clinical Pharmacist role to minimizing Adverse drug reaction, Drug related problems at ground level. He has to communicate with Physician and patient like messenger to solve the Drug related problems. We need to show our skills & knowledge towards therapeutic management and physician approaches to convince the obstacles on Drug related problems, Adverse drug reactions, Drug Interactions. So when we work together as health care professionals we can resolve all the problems and can provide better patient care services, Multiple drug regimens, co morbidities, patients age and medication errors has been found as the major cause of DRPs in our study. The study concludes that involving clinical pharmacist services in patients care can significantly helps to identify, resolve and prevent the DRPs in the hospital thereby enhancing the patient's outcomes. Furthermore, the suggestions provided by the clinical pharmacist during the intervention were well accepted by the physician thus the collaborative approach of physician and clinical pharmacist can provide better patients care outcomes. The study stresses the importance of clinical pharmacist in health care sector and impeccable role in patients care.

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